





In a laboratory study a full list of disinfectants was compiled to analyse their potential efficacy for control of *Clavibacter michiganensis* subsp. *sepedonicus*, *Dickeya solani*, *Dickeya dianthicola* and *Pectobacterium atrosepticum*. Because of its persistent nature, *Cms* is selected for studies under conditions true to practice in potato production systems.

Based on the promising results obtained under laboratory conditions, a practical study under strict phytosanitary quarantine containment is about to be started in spring 2015. Parallel tests will be performed in the laboratory to relate observations obtained under practical conditions. Products showing efficacy in disinfection of *Cms* on wood surfaces under laboratory conditions (in the dose rates of their authorisation in the Netherlands) will be tested in a practical setup with wooden boxes.

Although the practical application of the disinfection regime could only be tested on *Cms* within this project, it is likely that a similar regime will be equally effective against *Dickeya solani*, *Dickeya dianthicola* and *Pectobacterium atrosepticum* which are known to be less persistent in the natural environment than *Cms*. This hypothesis could be tested in a subsequent project under less stringent conditions as these bacteria are not subject to quarantine control.

Project ID: The effects of disinfection on *Clavibacter michiganensis* subsp. *sepedonicus* and other bacterial pathogens of potato in Europe (CMS-DISINFECT).